

PRIMARY PREVENTION OF IRON DEFICIENCY IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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The purpose of the study is to identify and assess current trends in the primary prevention of iron deficiency anemia in pregnant women (IDAPW) in the conditions of Andijan.

Research material and methods. A cross-sectional study of various prospective (2015-2020) epidemiological screening studies was organized. 1500 pregnant women aged 15-45 years were involved in it through a representative selection according to WHO criteria.

The population of pregnant women involved (PWI) was described as follows: hospital PWI, total urban and rural pregnant women - 1500: under 20 years - 48, 20 - 24 years - 636, 25 - 29 years - 481, 30 - 34 old people - 234, 35-39 years old - 79, 40-44 years old - 18 and over 45 years old - 4. Mean age (M+SD) – 26.1 ± 4.99 , height (M+SD) – 161.2 ± 6.0 cm and body weight (M+SD) – 67.6 ± 12.6 kg, body average percentage of weight deficit – 1.7%.

Normal weight PWI was 47.5%, overweight PWI was 34.9% and obese PWI was 17.5%.

In the examined PWI, the 1st level of obesity was 48.1%, the 2nd level was 3.5%, and the 3rd level was 0.9%.

All pregnant women (100.0%) belonged to indigenous population, 45.0% of them were rural residents and 55.0% were urban residents. 89.8% of pregnant women are housewives and 10.2% are working women ($R < 0.001$).

Epidemiological, demographic and clinical characteristics of the population of pregnant women included in this study are significantly different from similar characteristics presented in other regions.

General clinical, obstetric-gynecological, hematological, clinical-laboratory, instrumental, statistical and a total of 36 different screening methods were used. Internationally accepted and WHO recommended criteria were used for diagnosis of IDAPW.

In a non-experimental, prospective, simultaneous retro-analytic epidemiological study based on the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), epidemiological, biochemical, general clinical

obstetrics - gynecological, hematological clinical laboratory and instrumental and statistical methods were used.

The medical history of each pregnant woman was analyzed and evaluated according to special questionnaire questions: 1) subjective examination methods were carefully conducted and it included the following: information about the pregnant woman's complaints, medical history, life history, risk factors, and somatic diseases; 2) Medical supervision of pregnant women during the collection of Anamnesis morbi and Anamnesis vitae, adherence to anti-anemic treatments when symptoms of anemia are detected, and study of the characteristics of pregnancy.

All internal diseases leading to ID and IDS were studied and evaluated in the population of pregnant women under epidemiological monitoring.

All examinations were carried out in accordance with generally accepted screening and prevention rules, the methods recommended by WHO for epidemiological studies were used, and the examination program was followed.

Special biochemical testing methods. In accordance with generally accepted methods and requirements, a biochemical blood analysis was performed in the population of pregnant women; 1) 10 ml of blood was taken from the wrist vein on an empty stomach in the morning for blood analysis at the perinatal center. His serum was separated and the following were determined using a biochemical analyzer: total protein, potassium, sodium, bilirubin, glucose, urea, creatinine, blood lipid spectrum, alanine aminotransferase and aspartate aminotransferase (as needed).

The data of inspection, palpation, percussion and auscultation were carefully considered, the presence of hypovolemia was excluded. A detailed analysis of blood electrolytes and urine biochemical analysis was performed.

Hematological examinations. Hematological analyzes were performed based on modern approaches: 1) amount of hemoglobin, erythrocytes, leukocytes, erythrocyte indices, coagulogram and iron metabolism disorders: transport fund - serum iron and iron transferrin; reserve fund - serum ferritin.

Results and conclusions. In a prospective observation, the amount of hemoglobin in the blood (in g/l) and the dynamics of its 6-year changes were studied in the population of pregnant women aged ≥ 18 -45 years.

It has been shown that over 6 years of screening, the mean hemoglobin level in the general population of pregnant women decreased from 72.1 g/l to 66.1 g/l, i.e. by 6.0 g/l or less than 1 g/l per year. progress was noted.

It has been confirmed and proven that in the conditions of Andijan, there is a need to increase the primary prevention of iron deficiency/anemia in pregnant women at least twice. In addition, with the increase in the duration of pregnancy, a sharp decrease in the amount of hemoglobin in the blood and/or the risk of developing an iron deficiency state, IDAPW, has been proven in research.

